

Scalable Bio-Inspired Training of Deep Neural Networks with FastHebb

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Abstract

Recent work on sample efficient training of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) proposed a semi-supervised methodology based on biologically inspired Hebbian learning, combined with traditional backprop-based training. Promising results were achieved on various computer vision benchmarks, in scenarios of scarce labeled data availability. However, current Hebbian learning solutions can hardly address large-scale scenarios due to their demanding computational cost. In order to tackle this limitation, this contribution develops a novel solution by reformulating Hebbian learning rules in terms of matrix multiplications, which can be executed more efficiently on GPU. We experimentally show that the proposed approach, named FastHebb, accelerates training speed up to 70 times, allowing us to gracefully scale Hebbian learning experiments on large datasets and network architectures such as ImageNet and VGG.

Keywords: Hebbian Learning, Deep Learning, Neural Networks, Biologically Inspired

1. Introduction

Recent efforts from the research community focused on the development of biologically plausible alternative to the backpropagation algorithms for Deep Neural Network (DNN) training. Biological constraints require neurons to use only locally available information to compute the weight updates, and neuroscientific observations suggest that synaptic plasticity follows the *Hebbian* model [1, 2]. In simple terms, the weight update should be proportional to the input on the respective synapse and the neuron output at a given point in time. The study of biologically realistic learning models is interesting both because they are well suited for neuromorphic applications [3, 4], and for the perspective to better understand the mechanisms behind biological intelligence and use them to enhance current Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies.

Among the recently proposed bio-inspired learning approaches, Contrastive Hebbian Learning (CHL) [5] and Equilibrium Propagation (EP) [6] leverage recurrent architectures with Hebbian and anti-Hebbian

phases, showing that the resulting update steps approximate backprop. More recently, the Forward-Forward (FF) approach has been proposed [7] for feedforward networks, which is also based on an alternation between two phases. While the approaches mentioned above focus on supervised learning solutions, a lot of attention on bio-inspired methods has converged on unsupervised learning. For example, the Similarity Matching criterion [8, 9, 10, 11] or the Hebbian PCA rule [12, 13] allow neurons to learn to extract the principal components from data. Similarly, Hebbian learning with Winner-Takes-All (WTA) competition allows neurons to find clusters in the data space [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. This reveals interesting connections between the Hebbian theory of learning and data science.

In this work, we focus on a hybrid solution of unsupervised Hebbian learning and supervised backprop training, which are combined together in a semi-supervised fashion. In fact, supervised training alone has the disadvantage of requiring numerous training samples to achieve high performances, but the latter are often expensive to gather, requiring a consistent manual effort. To circumvent this issue, a possible direction is to pre-train the model on a large amount of unlabeled data, with an unsupervised algorithm, and then fine-tune with supervision on a small labeled dataset [21, 22]. In this scenario, recent work has shown superior performance of Hebbian-based semi-supervised

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50 training, compared to other unsupervised methods for
51 pre-training, such as Variational Auto-Encoders (VAE) 102
52 [23], especially in scenarios where the available labeled 103
53 data is scarce [13, 17]. Due to the difficulty of collect- 104
54 ing labeled data, these scenarios are of strong practical 105
55 interest. 106

56 Despite their promising results, current Hebbian 108
57 learning solutions can hardly be used to address large- 109
58 scale problems, due to their demanding computational 110
59 cost. In this perspective, the goal of our contribution is
60 to address the performance limitations of Hebbian algo- 111
61 rithms. For this purpose, we developed a new Hebbian 112
62 learning solution, named *FastHebb*, which is designed 113
63 to better take advantage of GPU acceleration. This is 114
64 done in two steps. First, we notice that Hebbian learning 115
65 with mini-batch processing evolves in two stages, one 116
66 is the weight update computation for each sample in the 117
67 mini-batch, and the other is the aggregation of updates
68 over all the minibatch elements. These two phases can 118
69 be merged together with a significant speedup. Second, 119
70 the resulting Hebbian equations of synaptic updates can
71 be translated in terms of matrix multiplications, which can 120
72 be executed very efficiently on GPU. 121

73 In order to provide an experimental evaluation of the 123
74 proposed method, we used established computer vision 124
75 benchmarks such as CIFAR10/100 [24], Tiny ImageNet
76 [25] and ImageNet [26]. Besides the image classifi-
77 cation evaluation, we also studied the performance of 125
78 Hebbian neural features for Content-Based Image Re-
79 trieval (CBIR). We considered sample efficient learn- 126
80 ing scenarios, where label information is assumed to
81 be available only for a certain percentage of the data 127
82 used for training. Results confirm previous observation 128
83 about the superior performance of Hebbian-based semi- 129
84 supervised approaches, compared to alternative solu- 130
85 tions, especially in label-scarce learning regimes. More- 131
86 over, the *FastHebb* solution exhibits a significant ac- 132
87 celeration of training times, both compared to previous 133
88 Hebbian learning solutions, and compared to backprop- 134
89 based alternatives. In particular, *FastHebb* achieves a 135
90 peak improvement in training up to 70 times faster than 136
91 corresponding Hebbian approaches not leveraging *FastHebb*. 137
92 This allowed to gracefully scale Hebbian algo- 138
93 rithms to large datasets, on the scale of ImageNet, 139
94 and architectures, on the scale of VGG [27]. Extending 140
95 Hebbian learning to other types of architectures, such 141
96 as residual networks [28] and transformers [29], in non- 142
97 trivial and deserves to be explored in a separate work. 143

98 Some of the results on *FastHebb* were already pre- 145
99 sented in our recent conference publication [30]. How- 146
100 ever, those results were just preliminary and the aim 147
101 of this paper is to significantly extend previous work. 148

102 Compared to [30], this paper performs a more compre-
103 hensive evaluation of the method by considering two
104 types of test scenarios, image classification and CBIR,
105 over four different computer vision benchmarks, includ-
106 ing ImageNet. Moreover, we also extend the range of
107 backbone architectures on which the approach is ap-
108 plied, pushing Hebbian learning to VGG-scale architec-
109 tures for the first time, as far as we know.

In summary, our contribution is twofold:

1. A scalable solution for Hebbian synaptic updates is proposed;
2. Extensive evaluation of Hebbian algorithms is presented, including new experiments on large-scale datasets (ImageNet) and architectures (VGG) which (to the best of our knowledge) have been out of reach for Hebbian algorithms so far.

Here is the structure of the following Sections: Section 2 illustrates related contributions; Section 3 describes the proposed *FastHebb* method more in detail; Section 4 delves into the details of our experimental scenarios in sample efficient and large-scale settings; in Section 5, the results of our experiments are described; conclusive remarks are presented in Section 6.

2. Background and related work

Some past contributions focused on addressing the biological plausibility problem of backpropagation by proposing solutions that can be shown to approximate backprop using Hebbian updates. Contrastive Hebbian Learning (CHL) [31] and Equilibrium Propagation (EP) [6] approaches do so by leveraging recurrent network architectures with two phases of activity. A free phase fixes the values of input neurons to represent a given sample, while output neurons and the remaining hidden units are left free. The recurrent dynamics lead the network to settle down into a steady state, where an anti-Hebbian update is performed. During the forced phase, the activations of output neurons are also fixed to a value closer to the desired target. Again, the recurrent dynamics will induce the network into another steady state, where a Hebbian update is performed. This combination of updates can be shown to approximate backprop at each neuron, using only local information. Another approach with strong biological support is Predictive Coding (PC) [32], in which a layer optimizes a local loss function that accounts for the error in predicting the next layer activations. Optimization is performed in a nested fashion. First, neuron activations are optimized to meet

149 the objective, which leads to the emergence of recur- 201
150 rent interactions among neurons, followed by optimiza- 202
151 tion of the weights. Again, the resulting updates can be 203
152 shown to match backprop updates using only local in- 204
153 formation [33]. The PC approach has been successfully 205
154 applied in different flavors to DNN training [34, 35, 36]. 206
155 More recently, the Forward-Forward (FF) approach has 207
156 been proposed [7]. This is based on standard feedfor- 208
157 ward architectures, but using an input vector composed 209
158 of both sample and target. The approach alternates a 210
159 positive phase, where sample and the correct target are 211
160 provided to the network, which is required to maximize 212
161 its activations, and a negative phase, where the sample 213
162 is paired with a randomly generated target, and the net- 214
163 work is required to minimize its activations. In a pre- 215
164 vious work [37], we have used a similar method for 216
165 training biologically realistic models of *in vitro* cultured 217
166 neural networks, where sample and target are provided 218
167 simultaneously to the network, and Hebbian plasticity 219
168 reinforces the connection between the two, so that at 220
169 test time, when a sample with no target is provided, the 221
170 network can recall the association. A weight normaliza-
171 tion mechanism plays the role of the negative phase in
172 this case.

173 In addition to these attempts to model supervised 223
174 learning from a biologically plausible perspective, other 224
175 efforts have been focused on modeling bio-inspired un- 225
176 supervised learning mechanisms. Past works used Heb- 226
177 bian learning with WTA competition models to train 227
178 feature extractors in feedforward and/or convolutional 228
179 CNNs [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20], showing impressive 229
180 convergence speed. In particular, a recent work [38] 230
181 showed that soft-WTA training of DNNs allows the net- 231
182 work to extract increasingly abstract representations, in 232
183 the same vein as backprop training, but at the cost of 233
184 using very wide layers. The authors also provide exper- 234
185 imental results with Hebbian learning on ImageNet, al- 235
186 though only for a single training epoch. The method that 236
187 we propose allows us to run a full training session (20 237
188 epochs or more) even on ImageNet scale. Miconi [39] 238
189 proposed translations of some Hebbian synaptic update 239
190 equations into optimizable objective functions, which 240
191 are more relatable to common frameworks for DL. An- 241
192 other line of research explored the *Similarity Matching* 242
193 objective as a possible direction to derive biologically 243
194 plausible neural models for principal subspace extrac- 244
195 tion [8, 9, 10, 11], with extensions also to the supervised 245
196 end-to-end recurrent training case [40, 41].

197 In our past contributions, we took a hybrid ap- 246
198 proach, and explored Hebbian WTA and PCA train- 247
199 ing of DNNs in semi-supervised scenarios, using unsu- 248
200 pervised Hebbian algorithms as a tool for pre-training 249

[12, 13, 42]. Experiments showed promising results, compared to backprop-based alternative methods, especially in scarce data learning scenarios. Due to the difficulty of gathering manually labeled data, these scenarios are of strong practical interest. Given the promising results obtained in previous works, in this contribution we further enhance previous solutions towards achieving higher efficiency and scalability to more complex scenarios.

Other works have explored semi-supervised approaches exploiting unsupervised pre-training with backprop-based auto-encoding architectures [43, 44, 21, 22]. A different direction towards semi-supervised learning is instead based on pseudo-labeling or consistency-based methods [45, 46, 47, 48]. Since our approach belongs to the unsupervised pre-training category, we will focus our comparisons in this setting. However, it is worth mentioning that the other approaches are not mutually exclusive with unsupervised pre-training, and, indeed, these can be integrated together, as also suggested in Sec. 6

3. Speeding Up Hebbian learning with FastHebb

In this Section we present the FastHebb method. We start by introducing a convenient notation, that will be used to translate Hebbian synaptic update equations into the FastHebb formulation. Then, we illustrate the learning rules that are analyzed in this work, and we derive their FastHebb-enhanced counterpart.

3.1. A convenient notation

When working with common packages for DL, such as Pytorch, data are typically represented as *tensors*. In this context, a tensor is simply a data array with multiple dimensions. We wish to introduce a notation for tensors that is better suited for relating mathematical formalism with the corresponding implementation in DL packages. For example, a tensor has a number of dimensions, whose interpretation lies in the mind of the programmer (e.g. batch, channel, height, and width dimensions for images). Given a tensor, packages such as Pytorch allow us to transpose or permute any of its dimensions, which corresponds to reordering indexes. We can also unsqueeze singleton dimensions or squeeze them out, which correspond to adding or removing *singleton* indexes, i.e. indexes of dimension 1. Therefore, in essence, the notation that we introduce is motivated by a more straightforward mapping to the programming formalism for working with tensors.

We consider tensors, denoted by capital letters, followed by one index per dimension. The symbol used

250 to denote the index denotes its meaning. For example, 296
 251 we can use an index $p = 1 \dots M$ to represent the *batch* 297
 252 dimension, an index $q = 1 \dots Q$ to represent the *chan-* 298
 253 *nel* dimension, and index $m = 1 \dots M$ to represent the 299
 254 *weight vector* dimension. A 1 symbol used as an index 300
 255 represents a singleton. For example, a neural feature 301
 256 map at some layer can be denoted as $A_{p,q,1}$, which is 302
 257 a tensor with one element for each mini-batch element 303
 258 (dimension p) and for each neuron (dimension q). The 304
 259 last dimension is a singleton because the output of each
 260 neuron for each mini-batch element is a scalar. Simi- 305
 261 larly, a weight matrix can be denoted by $B_{1,q,m}$, because 306
 262 it does not extend along the mini-batch dimension, but 307
 263 it has a number of channels (one per neuron), and each 308
 264 corresponds to a weight vector. Concerning the input 309
 265 tensors, for example images, they have a mini-batch, 310
 266 channel, height, and width dimensions. However, due to 311
 267 the convolutional processing, a patch will be extracted
 268 from each horizontal and vertical location of each im-
 269 age, which is treated, for the Hebbian learning purposes,
 270 as a separate input. Therefore, our mini-batch is the col-
 271 lection of all patches extracted from all images. Each
 272 patch is flattened into a vector, whose size corresponds
 273 to the weight vector size of the next neural layer. On the
 274 other hand, this tensor does not extend along the neu-
 275 ron dimension. Overall, our input tensors can be repre-
 276 sented as $C_{p,1,m}$.

277 This notation is convenient, because it allows us to
 278 easily swap indexes, or squeeze and unsqueeze sing-
 279 gleton dimensions. If tensors have compatible dimen- 312
 280 sions, we can also perform element-wise operations (ad- 313
 281 ditions, multiplications, etc.). When a dimension is 314
 282 a singleton, it automatically undergoes *broadcasting*,
 283 i.e. the tensor is replicated along that direction until it
 284 matches the corresponding dimension of the other ten-
 285 sor involved in the operation.

286 Matrix multiplication plays an important role in DNN 315
 287 processing. We make the usage of matrix multipli- 316
 288 cations explicit in our notation, by writing $\text{bmm}(\cdot, \cdot)$ 317
 289 (which stands for *batch matrix multiplication*): 318

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z_{i,j,l} &= \sum_k U_{i,j,k} V_{i,l,k} \\
 &= \sum_k U_{i,j,k} V_{i,l,k} := \text{bmm}(U_{i,j,k}, V_{i,l,k})
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

290 Notice that the matrix multiplication operation is 325
 291 equivalent to taking the element-wise product between 326
 292 tensors U and V , identifying the common index i and 327
 293 summing over (or *contracting*) index k . Specifically, in- 328
 294 dex i represents a batch dimension, and the operation 329
 295 is a batch matrix multiplication between i matrix pairs. 330

For each pair, the two matrices have indices (j, k) and
 (k, l) , which are mapped to indices (j, l) : $(j, k) \times (k, l) \rightarrow$
 (j, l) . The operation generalized to tensors with more
 that three dimensions as follows: all dimensions except
 the last two are considered as batch dimensions, while
 the last two dimensions represent rows and columns of
 the matrices being batch-multiplied. Batch dimensions
 must correspond between the two tensors, or be single-
 ton (in which case, broadcasting takes place).

3.2. Hebbian synaptic updates: from computation to aggregation

We consider two types of Hebbian learning rules:
 Hebbian PCA (HPCA) and soft-Winner-Takes-All
 (SWTA). In this paper, we just give the definition of
 these learning rules, but the interested reader can find
 more details in [20, 19, 13, 12].

Given a layer of neurons whose activations are de-
 noted by a_q (index q refers to the q -th neuron in the
 layer), whose weight vectors are denoted by \mathbf{b}_q , and
 whose input vector is denoted by \mathbf{c} , the SWTA synap-
 tic update equation is the following:

$$\Delta \mathbf{b}_q = \alpha s_q (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{b}_q) \tag{2}$$

Where α stands for the learning rate and s_q is the soft-
 max of the activations with temperature T [49]:

$$s_q = \frac{a_q/T}{\sum_k a_k/T} \tag{3}$$

Essentially, this modulates the update steps so that neu-
 rons with higher activations will also 'win' larger up-
 dates.

The HPCA learning rule, instead, is the following:

$$\Delta \mathbf{b}_q = \alpha a_q (\mathbf{c} - \sum_{k=1}^q a_k \mathbf{b}_k) \tag{4}$$

This rule can be shown to induce neurons to extract the
 principal components from data [50, 51].

When working with images and convolutional lay-
 ers, these weight updates need to be computed for each
 patch extracted from a given image. However, due to the
 constraints of convolutional layers, neurons at different
 offsets need to maintain shared weights, hence they are
 bound to follow the same synaptic modifications. This
 can be achieved by aggregating the different weight up-
 dates, obtained from patches at different locations, into
 a unique update. Aggregation needs to be performed
 for all the images in a mini-batch as well. The overall
 two-phases approach is depicted in Fig. 1.

Aggregation is performed simply by averaging, in
 the HPCA case, or by a weighted average, where the
 weights are s_q coefficients, for SWTA.

Figure 1: Two phases of weight update: update computation for each patch, followed by aggregation of several updates.

3.3. From Hebbian synaptic updates to FastHebb

The Hebbian rules presented above can be rewritten in matrix form, including the aggregation step, using the notation outlined at the beginning of this Section:

$$\Delta B_{1,q,m} = \sum_p D_{p,q,1} \Delta B_{p,q,m} = \text{bmm}(D_{q,1,p}, \Delta B_{q,p,m}) \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta B_{p,q,m}$ is the collection of all weight updates that need to be aggregated, and $D_{p,q,1}$ is the tensor of coefficients for the aggregation.

Now that the two phases of weight computation and aggregation are merged together, we proceed differently depending on the specific learning rule.

FastHebb for SWTA. Let's rewrite the SWTA update rule as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta B_{1,q,m} &= \alpha \sum_p D_{p,q,1} S_{p,q,1} (C_{p,1,m} - B_{1,q,m}) \\ &= \alpha \sum_p (DS)_{p,q,1} (C - B)_{p,q,m} \\ &= \alpha \text{bmm}((DS)_{q,1,p}, (C - B)_{q,p,m}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Where $D_{p,q,1} = \frac{S_{p,q,1}}{\sum_p S_{p,q,1}}$.

The computational complexity required by this algorithm is $O(PQM)$ in time. Moreover, if we wish to

exploit GPU parallelism, we need to keep a $P \times Q \times M$ tensor in memory, thus requiring $O(PQM)$ space complexity as well, which can be prohibitive for large-scale scenarios.

However, it is possible to improve over these bounds by contracting the aggregation index p (which is typically the largest dimension) early:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta B_{1,q,m} &= \alpha \sum_p D_{p,q,1} S_{p,q,1} (C_{p,1,m} - B_{1,q,m}) \\ &= \alpha \sum_p (DS)_{p,q,1} C_{p,1,m} - \alpha \sum_p (DS)_{p,q,1} B_{1,q,m} \\ &= \alpha \text{bmm}((DS)_{1,q,m}, C_{1,q,m}) - \alpha \sum_p (DS)_{p,q,1} B_{1,q,m} \\ &= \alpha \text{bmm}((DS)_{1,q,p}, C_{1,p,m}) - \alpha E_{1,q,1} B_{1,q,m} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where $E_{1,q,1} = \sum_p (DS)_{p,q,1}$.

This requires only $O(Q(P + M))$ space complexity. Concerning the time complexity, this depends on the specific matrix multiplication algorithm adopted, but this can be made lower than $O(PQM)$. This is the FastHebb formulation for SWTA.

FastHebb for HPCA. Similarly to the SWTA case, we can rewrite the HPCA equation, together with the aggregation phase (in this case, the coefficient $D_{p,q,1}$ is just $\frac{1}{P}$), with the proposed notation:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta B_{1,q,m} &= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_p A_{p,q,1} \left(C_{p,1,m} - \sum_{q'=1}^q A_{p,q',1} B_{1,q',m} \right) \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_p A_{p,q,1} \left(C_{p,1,m} - \sum_{q'=1}^Q T_{q,q'} A_{p,q',1} B_{1,q',m} \right) \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_p A_{p,q,1} F_{p,q,m} \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \text{bmm}(A_{q,1,p}, F_{q,p,m})
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Where $F_{p,q,m} = (C_{p,1,m} - \sum_{q'=1}^Q T_{q,q'} A_{p,q',1} B_{1,q',m})$, and $T_{q,q'}$ is simply a lower-triangular matrix with all ones on and below the main diagonal and all zeros above.

The computation of the HPCA equation is slightly more complex, requiring $O(PQ^2M)$ space and time, but this can be improved by reordering the sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta B_{1,q,m} &= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_p A_{p,q,1} \left(C_{p,1,m} - \sum_{q'=1}^Q T_{q,q'} A_{p,q',1} B_{1,q',m} \right) \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_p A_{p,q,1} C_{p,1,m} \\
&\quad - \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_p A_{p,q,1} \sum_{q'=1}^Q T_{q,q'} A_{p,q',1} B_{1,q',m} \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \text{bmm}(A_{1,q,p}, C_{1,p,m}) \\
&\quad - \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_{q'=1}^Q \sum_p A_{p,q,1} A_{p,q',1} T_{q,q'} B_{1,q',m} \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \text{bmm}(A_{1,q,p}, C_{1,p,m}) \\
&\quad - \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_{q'=1}^Q \text{bmm}(A_{1,q,p}, A_{1,p,q'}) T_{q,q'} B_{1,q',m} \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \text{bmm}(A_{1,q,p}, C_{1,p,m}) \\
&\quad - \alpha \frac{1}{P} \sum_{q'=1}^Q G_{1,q,q'} B_{1,q',m} \\
&= \alpha \frac{1}{P} \text{bmm}(A_{1,q,p}, C_{1,p,m}) \\
&\quad - \alpha \frac{1}{P} \text{bmm}(G_{1,q,q'}, B_{1,q',m})
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Where, $G_{1,q,q'} = \text{bmm}(A_{1,q,p}, A_{1,p,q'}) T_{q,q'}$.

The overall computation now has $O(Q^2 + QM)$ complexity in space, and up to $O(PQM + PQ^2 + Q^2M)$ in time. This is the FastHebb formulation for HPCA.

4. Evaluation scenario

We evaluated the proposed methodology on a number of established computer vision benchmarks: CIFAR10/100 [24], Tiny ImageNet [25], and ImageNet [26]. We performed an evaluation of Hebbian-based approaches in semi-supervised learning settings, on a backbone network model described in the following, compared to a Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) [23, 21] baseline. In addition, we provide a FastHebb evaluation on VGG [27], to show the scalability of the proposed approach to large architectures. We evaluated the performance both in terms of classification accuracy, and in terms of training speedup achieved with FastHebb. We also provide an evaluation of Hebbian neural features for large-scale image retrieval tasks.

4.1. Neural network backbone for evaluation

In order to provide an evaluation for the proposed approach, we need to define a suitable backbone network architecture for our experiments. For this purpose, we need a network that presents the common architectural features of Convolutional Neural Networks (pooling and convolutional layers [52], batch normalization [53], etc.). On the other hand, we need to exclude more recent features such as residual connections [28] or attention layers [29], for Hebbian algorithms are not trivial to generalize to these cases, which deserve to be analyzed in a separate work. For a first experimentation stage, we do not need to consider a very large model; it is instead preferable to consider a more compact architecture, which enables faster experimentation, and easier analysis of deep features, also on a layer-by-layer basis. It also makes reproducibility by other researchers more accessible. Therefore, we opted for an AlexNet-inspired [52] architecture shown in Fig. 2, with 6 layers, which is also consistent with previous works [20, 30]. For larger-scale experiments on ImageNet we used an extended version of the previous model with 10 layers, shown in Fig. 3, as well as a VGG model [27].

4.2. Semi-supervised training protocol for sample-efficient learning

We evaluated the proposed approach assuming a condition of scarcity of available labeled training data. We define a *sample efficiency* regime as the percentage of available labeled samples, over the total number of

Figure 2: Backbone neural network model used for our experiments.

Figure 3: Bigger neural network model for ImageNet experiments.

415 training samples. For each of the considered datasets, 466
 416 we performed experiments in eight different sample efficiency 467
 417 regimes: 1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, 5%, 10%, 25%, and 468
 418 100%. 469

419 In order to take advantage of both labeled and unlabeled 470
 420 training samples, for each sample efficiency regime, we followed a semi-supervised training proto- 471
 421 col in two phases: first, the network is pre-trained using 472
 422 one of the proposed unsupervised Hebbian algorithms, 473
 423 exploiting all the available training samples; second, 474
 424 end-to-end fine-tuning is performed, using supervised 475
 425 backprop training on a cross-entropy loss, and exploit- 476
 426 ing the labeled samples only. Finally, both the resulting 477
 427 classification accuracy and the training time (in terms of 478
 428 epoch duration, number of epochs, and total duration) 479
 429 were recorded. 480

431 As a baseline for comparison, we used unsupervised 482
 432 pre-training based on the Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) 483
 433 approach [54]. In this case, pre-training was 484
 434 performed by using the deep layers (excluding the final 485
 435 classifier) of the proposed architectures as encoder, 486
 436 mapping their output to 256 gaussian latent variables. 487
 437 This was augmented with a another network branch, 488
 438 acting as decoder, with a specular structure w.r.t. the en- 489
 439 coder (i.e. pooling layers replaced with unpooling, and 490
 440 convolutions with transpose convolutions), mapping the 491
 441 latent variables to a decoded sample. The overall mod- 492
 442 els were trained in the encoding-decoding task, opti- 493
 443 mizing the β -VAE Variational Lower Bound [55], in an 494
 444 end to end fashion, using all the available training sam- 495
 445 ples. At this point, the decoder was dropped, a linear 496
 446 classifier was placed on top of the latent features, and 497
 447 supervised backprop-based end-to-end fine tuning was 498
 448 performed, using only the available labeled samples for 499
 449 the given sample efficiency regime. Essentially, this is 500
 450 the standard semi-supervised training approach based 501
 451 on state-of-the-art VAE architectures [21]. Notice that 502
 452 in this case, however, the pre-training phase, even if un- 503
 453 supervised, is still backprop-based, while Hebbian algo- 504
 454 rithms enable pre-training without requiring backprop. 505

4.3. Retrieval with neural features

456 Deep features extracted from pre-trained networks 500
 457 were also used as vector descriptors for multimedia con- 501
 458 tent indexing and retrieval [56, 57, 58]. The perfor- 502
 459 mance of the resulting feature representation was eval- 503
 460 uated in Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) tasks. 504

461 The CBIR systems architecture works as follows: in 505
 462 a first phase, feature representations are computed for 506
 463 all images in a given database, by extracting the deep 507
 464 representations from the convolutional part of the net- 508
 465 work. These feature representations are then mapped 509

to a binary 256-dimensional descriptor which is then 466
 used for indexing the database images. This is done 467
 as in [57] by training another piece of network, with 468
 a 256 units hidden layer with tanh activations and a fi- 469
 nal classifier. This is trained in the classification task, 470
 so that the feature representation is mapped to the cor- 471
 rect class, but passing through a compression stage into 472
 the desired 256 dimensional vector. The tanh activation 473
 is a "soft" proxy for the binarization operation, which 474
 doesn't block gradients from flowing backward during 475
 training. The 256 dimensional representation is then bi- 476
 naryzed by a thresholding operation: positive values are 477
 mapped to 1 and negative values are mapped to 0. 478

479 Test set images are used as sample queries: at test 480
 time, their 256-dimensional binary feature representa- 481
 tion is computed as well, and the database images are 482
 ranked against the query based on the Hamming dist- 483
 ance between feature representations. Retrieved imag- 484
 es are considered to be a correct match if they belong 485
 to the same class as the query. 486

The evaluation measure used for the CBIR task is the 487
 Average Precision Score (APS) :

$$APS = \sum_{i=1}^K P_i (R_i - R_{i-1}) \quad (10)$$

487 where P_i is the precision at the i^{th} retrieved item, R_i is 488
 489 the corresponding recall. This score is renormalized (so 490
 491 that its maximum value is always 1) and averaged over 492
 all the queries, thus obtaining the mean Average Preci- 493
 sion (mAP). 494

4.4. Implementation details

495 The experiments, implemented in Pytorch, depend on 500
 496 a number of hyperparameters, whose search was pur- 501
 497 sued by Coordinate Descent (CD) [59], optimizing, for 502
 498 each dataset, the accuracy results of the trained models 503
 499 on the respective validation set. In the following, the 504
 500 resulting parameters and implementation details are il- 505
 501 lustrated. 506

507 All training sessions were performed over 20 epochs 508
 509 (which were enough for the models to converge). Data 500
 510 were processed in mini-batches of 64 samples each, 501
 511 and each sample was an RGB image of 32 pixels in 502
 512 height and width for the 6-layer CIFAR10/100 and Tiny 503
 513 ImageNet network, 210 pixels for the 10-layer Image- 504
 514 Net network, and 224 pixels for VGG (specifically, 505
 515 the VGG-11 model was used), pre-normalized to zero 506
 516 mean and unit variance. 507

517 Concerning Hebbian pre-training, the learning rate 508
 518 parameter was set to 10^{-3} . For ImageNet training, we 509

510 also introduced an adaptive learning rate mechanism to 558
511 cope with the high variance of weight updates due to the 559
512 high dimensionality of the feature maps (causing insta- 560
513 bility during training), which divides the learning rate 561
514 by the square root of the input size (this corresponds 562
515 to normalizing the output variance, assuming the inputs 563
516 are normalized). For SWTA training only, whitening 564
517 pre-processing was also necessary, as in [60, 24], al- 565
518 though this step did not show any benefit on the other
519 approaches. SWTA uses 0.02 as inverse temperature pa-
520 rameter $1/T$.

521 Batch-norm layers used momentum 0.9.

522 Backprop-based training (i.e. both fine-tuning and 569
523 VAE pre-training) leveraged Stochastic Gradient De- 570
524 scent (SGD) optimization with learning rate 10^{-3} , and 571
525 momentum 0.9, with Nesterov acceleration [61]. After 572
526 10 training epochs, learning rate was reduced by half 573
527 every 2 epochs until the end of the training session. The 574
528 best training epoch in terms of validation results was 575
529 then selected as final model (early stopping). 576

530 β -VAE training used coefficient $\beta = 0.5$.

531 Supervised fine-tuning was regularized by dropout 577
532 with 0.5 rate, and L_2 weight decay with penalty equal 578
533 to $5 \cdot 10^{-2}$, 10^{-2} , $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$, $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$, for CIFAR10, CI- 579
534 FAR100, Tiny ImageNet, ImageNet, respectively.

535 The implementation used Pytorch version 1.8.1 and
536 Python 3.7, with an Ubuntu 20.4 system running on
537 an I7 series 10700K Intel Processor, 32GB RAM, and
538 12GB NVidia Geforce 3060 GPU.

539 5. Results

540 The results of the experiments described in the pre- 581
541 vious Section are illustrated hereafter. First, we re- 582
542 port the recorded training speed, in terms of epoch du- 583
543 ration, number of epochs for convergence, and total 584
544 duration, on CIFAR10/100, Tiny ImageNet, and Ima- 585
545 geNet datasets, comparing VAE pre-training, ordinary 586
546 Hebbian learning, and FastHebb. Second, we report 587
547 the classification and retrieval results of the various ap- 588
548 proaches in the label-scarcity scenarios described ear- 589
549 lier. Finally, we report the results on the VGG archi- 590
550 tecture as well. The results were obtained from averag-
551 ing five independent experiment iterations, and t-testing
552 confirmed the observed differences to be statistically
553 significant with p-values below 0.05.

554 5.1. Training speed analysis

555 Table 1 shows a comparison between the considered 599
556 approaches in terms of computational performance of 600
557 training, on the 10-layer (for ImageNet) and 6-layer (for

the other datasets) architectures. The Table shows the
single epoch duration, the number of epochs until con-
vergence (measured as the point after which validation
results stop improving), and the total training duration¹.
These results are specifically focused on the pre-training
duration, while we observed no statistically significant
difference in the duration of the successive fine-tuning
phase for different pre-training approaches.

We can observe that FastHebb methods are signif-
icantly faster (up to 50 times for HPCA and HPCA-
FH on ImageNet) than the traditional Hebbian coun-
terparts, with an epoch duration becoming comparable
to backprop-based VAE training. This enables Hebbian
approaches to scale gracefully to complex datasets such
as ImageNet, where the best speed-up by a factor of
50, in terms of epoch duration, is observed for HPCA.
Moreover, the overall training duration of Hebbian ap-
proaches becomes faster (up to 5 times on ImageNet)
than VAE, thanks to the lower number of epochs re-
quired to convergence. Among the Hebbian approaches,
soft-WTA has lower time complexity, and it is in fact
faster.

580 5.2. Label scarcity results

581 Table 2 illustrates the classification results, in terms
582 of accuracy (top-1 for CIFAR10, and top-5 for the other
583 datasets, since they contain many more classes), in var-
584 ious sample efficiency regimes, comparing the alterna-
585 tive approaches. Notice that in the results for HPCA and
586 SWTA there is no difference between using FastHebb
587 or not. In fact, despite the computational speedup, from
588 the algebraic point of view FastHebb is equivalent to
589 ordinary Hebbian learning, leading to the same results.
590 Therefore, we show these results just once.

591 The results show that, in conditions of label scarcity
592 (sample efficiency regimes below 4-5%), Hebbian ap-
593 proaches perform significantly better than VAE. On the
594 other hand, it is only when far more labels are available
595 for the supervised fine-tuning phase that VAE-based
596 pre-training really kicks in. In these scenarios, however,
597 the performance of Hebbian approaches is comparable
598 or only slightly lower, but this is compensated by the
599 speedup in training time observed before. Comparing
600 HPCA and SWTA, it appears that the former performs
601 typically better.

Table 1: Analysis of algorithm performance on each dataset, for VAE, Hebbian PCA (HPCA), Hebbian PCA with FastHebb (HPCA-FH), soft-WTA (SWTA), and soft-WTA with FastHebb (SWTA-FH) methods, on the 10-layer (for ImageNet) and 6-layer (for the other datasets) networks.

Dataset	Method	Epoch Duration	Num. Epochs	Total Duration
CIFAR10	VAE	14s	17	3m 58s
	SWTA	4m 14s	1	4m 14s
	SWTA-FH	18s	1	18s
	HPCA	6m 23s	12	1h 16m 36s
	HPCA-FH	19s	12	3m 48s
CIFAR100	VAE	15s	15	3m 45s
	SWTA	4m 16s	1	4m 16s
	SWTA-FH	18s	1	18s
	HPCA	6m 25s	7	44m 55s
	HPCA-FH	19s	7	2m 13s
Tiny ImageNet	VAE	33s	20	11m
	SWTA	9m 41s	1	9m 41s
	SWTA-FH	41s	1	41s
	HPCA	14m 20s	14	3h 20m 40s
	HPCA-FH	43s	14	10m 2s
ImageNet	VAE	2h 59m 19s	16	47h 49m 4s
	SWTA	105h 13m 24s	3	315h 40m 12s
	SWTA-FH	3h 38m 6s	3	10h 54m 18s
	HPCA	155h 41m 39s	3	467h 4m 57s
	HPCA-FH	3h 39m 18s	3	10h 57m 54s

5.3. Retrieval experiments

Table 3 shows the retrieval mAP results obtained on the various dataset, for each of the considered approaches, on the 10-layer (for ImageNet) and 6-layer (for the other datasets) architectures.

This second scenario confirms the previous observations that, in conditions of extreme label scarcity (below 10%), Hebbian-based neural features achieve better results than VAE counterparts. Again, VAE-based pre-training improves in higher regimes, but, as observed before, this is fairly compensated by the training time advantage of Hebbian approaches. Comparing HPCA and SWTA, also in this case it appears that the former performs typically better.

5.4. Experiments on VGG

In Tab. 5, we report the training times required for the pre-training phase of VGG models using the different approaches considered so far. We do not consider VAE-type training of the VGG model, because that requires a large decoder, making the overall model very deep,

which we found to be untrainable due to vanishing gradients [62, 63]. On the other hand, Hebbian pre-training was straightforward to apply in this case, as it requires no gradient backpropagation. Instead, as a baseline for comparison, we used Xavier initialization [64] (note that, since this is not properly a training method, it is not included in Tab. 5). In fact, it is known that appropriate initialization methods can achieve competitive results compared to end-to-end pre-training [64, 65].

Training times show once more the effectiveness of FastHebb methods in training large scale architectures, while using ordinary Hebbian learning would be unfeasible. In the best case, a speedup of almost 70 times is reached, comparing HPCA-FH with HPCA.

Finally, in Tab. 5, we report the results, both in terms of classification accuracy and retrieval mAP, achieved by training the VGG model in the semi-supervised task. We show the results achieved with Xavier initialization, HPCA pre-training, and SWTA pre-training.

When the scale of the architecture increases, it appears that SWTA approach improves over HPCA. Previous observations about Hebbian methods performing better in low sample efficiency regimes (5% and below) are confirmed. In particular, SWTA outperforms the network with no pre-training by a margin up to 5 percentage points in accuracy, in the 1-2% sample efficiency

¹For Hebbian approaches not using FastHebb, the training duration would be unfeasible to measure explicitly; instead, it was estimated by multiplying the single epoch duration by the number of epochs

Table 2: Accuracy results on each dataset (top-1 for CIFAR10, and top-5 for the other datasets, since they have many more classes), for the various approaches explored, on the 10-layer (for ImageNet) and 6-layer (for the other datasets) networks.

Regime	Method	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	Tiny ImageNet	ImageNet
1%	VAE	22.54	12.28	5.55	2.72
	SWTA	30.23	15.30	6.20	6.69
	HPCA	39.75	22.63	11.38	8.65
2%	VAE	26.78	15.25	6.74	6.14
	SWTA	36.59	20.76	8.56	11.52
	HPCA	45.51	30.83	15.71	13.64
3%	VAE	29.00	16.44	7.74	15.35
	SWTA	41.54	23.69	10.26	15.67
	HPCA	48.80	35.04	18.23	17.28
4%	VAE	31.15	17.89	8.45	23.97
	SWTA	45.31	26.91	11.52	19.95
	HPCA	51.28	38.89	20.55	20.39
5%	VAE	32.75	18.48	9.29	29.04
	SWTA	48.35	29.57	12.55	24.87
	HPCA	52.20	41.42	22.46	23.28
10%	VAE	45.67	23.80	13.51	43.73
	SWTA	58.00	38.26	16.70	41.54
	HPCA	57.35	48.93	28.13	34.27
25%	VAE	68.70	52.59	37.89	61.33
	SWTA	69.85	56.26	24.96	59.34
	HPCA	64.77	58.70	37.10	56.92
100%	VAE	85.23	79.97	60.23	76.84
	SWTA	85.37	79.80	54.94	76.10
	HPCA	84.38	74.42	53.96	77.28

648 regimes. In terms of mAP, Hebbian pre-training is still
649 slightly superior, although the difference is not statisti-
650 cally significant.

651 6. Conclusions and future work

652 In this article, we have illustrated the FastHebb ap-
653 proach for Hebbian learning, which leverages a matrix
654 multiplication formulation of Hebbian synaptic updates
655 to achieve higher efficiency. This makes Hebbian learn-
656 ing more scalable, enabling the use of Hebbian neural
657 features also on large datasets (ImageNet) and architec-
658 tures (VGG), which (to the best of our knowledge) have
659 been computationally prohibitive for Hebbian learning
660 so far. Experimental scenarios of label scarcity show
661 promising results of Hebbian pre-training compared to
662 backprop-based alternatives such as VAE, considering
663 classification accuracy, retrieval mAP, and training time.

664 Even though, in this paper, we have shown that it is
665 possible to scale Hebbian training to large models such
666 as VGG, further work needs to be done to adapt Heb-
667 bian approaches to more recent architectures, such as

668 residual networks [28] or Transformers [29]. Moreover,
669 additional performance improvements might come from
670 the combination of Hebbian-based pre-training with
671 pseudo-labeling and consistency-based semi-supervised
672 methods [66, 48]. Finally, in line with recent efforts
673 towards backprop-free learning (such as the Forward-
674 Forward algorithm [7]), we plan to explore strategies
675 to combine Hebbian approaches with local supervision
676 signals.

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Table 3: mAP results on each dataset, for the various approaches explored, on the 10-layer (for ImageNet) and 6-layer (for the other datasets) networks.

Regime	Method	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	Tiny ImageNet	ImageNet
1%	VAE	21.90	6.10	3.18	0.95
	SWTA	28.29	8.16	3.80	1.94
	HPCA	37.39	15.39	6.61	4.88
2%	VAE	23.13	6.40	3.20	1.39
	SWTA	31.71	8.82	3.95	2.54
	HPCA	39.80	15.98	7.39	5.72
3%	VAE	24.27	6.36	3.52	2.02
	SWTA	34.54	9.13	4.16	3.21
	HPCA	41.64	16.40	7.57	6.56
4%	VAE	24.36	6.36	3.57	3.83
	SWTA	36.54	9.41	4.32	3.77
	HPCA	43.22	16.72	7.61	7.19
5%	VAE	24.65	6.49	3.57	5.49
	SWTA	38.69	9.66	4.39	4.19
	HPCA	44.92	17.10	7.79	7.75
10%	VAE	28.26	7.09	3.76	13.27
	SWTA	48.55	11.27	5.01	9.14
	HPCA	49.99	18.42	8.45	10.56
25%	VAE	62.30	13.69	7.59	24.50
	SWTA	63.95	16.37	6.98	20.75
	HPCA	58.81	21.49	10.13	21.24
100%	VAE	84.67	42.83	22.64	44.21
	SWTA	84.54	43.95	20.86	39.60
	HPCA	81.80	36.19	17.99	43.81

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Table 4: Comparison of ImageNet training times, for Hebbian PCA (HPCA), Hebbian PCA with FastHebb (HPCA-FH), soft-WTA (SWTA), and soft-WTA with FastHebb (SWTA-FH) methods, on VGG-11.

Dataset	Method	Epoch Duration	Num. Epochs	Total Duration
ImageNet	SWTA	290h 44m	5	1454h
	SWTA-FH	7h 7m	5	35h 35m
	HPCA	453h 32m	13	5896h
	HPCA-FH	6h 25m	13	83h 25m

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Table 5: Accuracy results on ImageNet (top-5), and retrieval mean Average Precision (mAP) for the various approaches explored, on the VGG network.

Regime	Pre-train	Accuracy (%)	mAP (%)
1%	None	14.71	4.79
	SWTA	19.40	3.63
	HPCA	15.53	5.16
2%	None	26.88	6.42
	SWTA	31.91	5.18
	HPCA	27.24	6.70
3%	None	36.68	8.05
	SWTA	40.24	7.08
	HPCA	36.74	8.05
4%	None	44.01	9.34
	SWTA	46.98	8.95
	HPCA	43.69	9.68
5%	None	49.37	10.80
	SWTA	51.36	10.47
	HPCA	50.40	10.92
10%	None	65.61	17.44
	SWTA	65.09	17.53
	HPCA	65.49	17.65
25%	None	78.71	29.01
	SWTA	78.17	29.52
	HPCA	78.53	29.20
100%	None	90.03	50.58
	SWTA	88.00	49.93
	HPCA	88.54	50.06

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